

Collate 2, and the design for its successor: CollateXML (now, CollateX)

Historical note: the contexts of this document

The article which follows was posted on the Scholarly Digital Editions blog in a series of entries from February to June 2007. There were two contexts for these original blog posts:

1. The age, and impending death, of *Collate 2*, the computer-assisted scholarly collation program I had started writing in the late 1980s. This had achieved some success, at least by the simple measure that it was one of the rare "humanities computing" (as we used to call it) computer programs used by people other than the person who wrote it. So we used it in the Canterbury Tales project to make some six digital editions; Prue Shaw used it to make her editions of Dante's *Monarchia* and *Commedia* (see www.sd-editions.com); the Greek New Testament editing projects at Munster and Birmingham made it the centre of their moves into the digital age; Michael Stolz used it for his edition of *Parzival* (www.parzival.unibe.ch/home.html). *Collate 2* was written for classic Macintosh computers, and the advent of OS X from 2002 on first cast a doubt on the future of the "classic" operating system, and then became a death sentence when Apple announced in 2005 that OS X was moving to Intel processors, and that when it did make this move, the classic system would die. Of course, I could have rewritten *Collate* for OS X. However, it was clear that this was no simple matter. The heart of *Collate* was (and is) a series of interactive routines, allowing the scholar to control the collation through multiple dialogue boxes: over a hundred of them, all told. OS X introduced a quite different (and vastly superior) model for handling interactive dialogues; every one of these venerable "event loops" would have to be rewritten. I could have done this, but by this time, I was aware that there were fundamental things which *Collate* could not do. Sometimes, you can renovate. Sometimes, you have to rebuild from the ground up.

2. As I was mulling this over from 2005 on, I began to talk to two people in particular who were interested in computer scholarly collation systems: Fotis Iannidis, the director of TextGrid, and Joris Van Zundert, engaged in software systems development at the Huygens Institute. Both Fotis and Joris had a vital scholarly interest in collation, and both might have access to resources (which might need to be considerable) to write a successor to *Collate*. In late January 2007, Joris convened a meeting in The Hague to discuss editing software systems, including collation; in early 2008, Fotis came to Birmingham to discuss how we might proceed.

This blog post was directly stimulated, then, by the meeting with Joris and others in 2007. It is an attempt to lay out what I thought might be fundamental to a useful successor to *Collate*. At the time, I said, half-jokingly, that it took me about five years on my own to write the first version of *Collate*; it would take ten people ten years to write its successor. Following these meetings, by various indirections, the InterEdition project (bringing together Huygens and TextGrid people) got started. A group loosely based within InterEdition took on what quickly became known as CollateX, with Ronald Dekker particularly taking on writing the core software routines. A look at the CollateX site, some seven years on, suggests that my idle prediction was not too far astray.

Now, the original blog posts, as posted between 12.58 pm GST, 5 February 2007 and 10.02 pm, 28 June 2007. I follow this with an email I sent to Fotis, Joris and others announcing these posts. Among other matters: the post of June 21 announces the new name: CollateX. Thus it has been since.

February 5, 2007

The design of CollateXML

Filed under: Designing Collate – Peter @ 12:58 pm

In this document I set out, as clearly as I can, the various datastructures and operations which I think CollateXML will require.

The fundamental design of CollateXML is this:

1. The input is various streams of text, divided into marked collation blocks
2. These various streams of text are located
3. Within the streams of text, each corresponding block for collation must be located
4. The collation program creates two sets of collation information:
 1. concerning the different orderings of the blocks within the streams of text
 2. concerning the differences in the texts contained in the blocks themselves

The collation information is then formatted for output

A few observations:

1. In Collate0-2, the input was always computer files, held on the computer itself. In CollateXML, the input could be 'any text, anywhere': from a database, local or remote; from a URL anywhere.
2. The crucial marking of collation blocks should be done through something like the 'universal text identifier' scheme I outlined at The Hague on 25 January 2007.
3. Collate0-2 did only 'word by word' collation. This presumes that the texts are 'word by word' collatable: without very large areas of added, deleted, or transposed text. But many texts have a different kind of relation: large portions of one text might be embedded in another text, but other areas of the texts are very different (the situation common in plagiarism, or 'intertextuality', for example). Collate0-2 did not handle this situation; CollateXML should be able to do so.
4. CollateXML should have its own internal data models for passing information both to and from the collation process. These models should be exposed through an API to programmers, who can then provide import and export for whatever formats they choose.

We can now begin to specify the building blocks we need.

February 5, 2007

How CollateXML should work

Filed under: How CollateXML should work – Peter @ 1:18 pm

The separation of collation into stages

As Collate0-2 developed, I learnt that one had to break the collation process into stages. At first, Collate 0-2 simply collated, and identified the variants as it found them. I soon learned that the complex requirements of scholarly collation demanded the adjustment of the collation at various points. To do this, it became clear that one had to separate out the stages of collation to permit intervention at various points. However, this separation was grafted onto Collate0-2 in a piecemeal fashion. I propose that from the beginning, CollateXML separate out what appear to me now as the following fundamental stages of collation:

1. text alignment, one witness at a time against the base
2. storage of alignment information for all witnesses against the base
3. adjustment of alignment information for all witnesses against each other

4. variant identification within the aligned texts.

Text alignment

The fundamental building block is the alignment routine itself. Here is how I suggest this works for word by word collation, based on how it worked in Collate 0-2.

1. Each alignment act compares two texts of a text block at once: a specified 'base' text and a witness text. starting at the first word of the text block in each
2. The alignment examines the first word: if they are identical it returns this information; if there is a variant it returns that information along with: the number of words matched in base text and witness text. The possibilities are:
 1. same word in each. 1 word matched in each; next word to match in base will be word 2; next word to match in witness will be word 2
 2. one word replacing one word in each. next word to match in base will be word 2; next word to match in witness will be word 2
 3. word omitted in witness. next word to match in base will be 2; next word to match in witness will be
 4. word added in witness. next word to match in base will be 1; next word to match in witness will be 2
 5. phrase omission or addition: as for c and d, but the next word to be matched in base or witness will be adjusted accordingly
 6. phrase replacement: if two words in the base are replaced by three words in the witness: then the next word in the base to be collated for this witness will be word 3; the next word to be collated in the witness will be word 4.

This is, fundamentally, rather simple. You can look over the C code for Collate 2 to see how we did this. Essentially, at each alignment, Collate 2 carried out a series of tests, till it got a match:

1. are the next words identical?
2. are the next words a variant, and so align against each other? Collate used a 'fuzzy match' algorithm for this. Essentially, if the two words had more than 50% of their letters in common (weighted according to the position of the letters) then Collate said, these words align. Thus, Collate would see 'cat' and 'mat' as variants on each other
3. it could be that while this word does not match, the next word does. So Collate will look at 'black cat' and 'white cat' and declare that 'black' and 'white' align, because the next word is a match. Indeed, Collate would look at 'black cat' and 'white mat', see that mat/cat align because they satisfy the fuzzy match test, and so declare black/white align
4. If there is still no match: collate tests the second word in the master against the first word in the witness. If they match: Collate concludes that the first word in the master is omitted.
5. Still no match: collate tests the second word in the witness against the first word in the base. If they match: Collate concludes that the first word in the witness has been added. Now, here is an important point: after establishing that the first word in the witness has been added, Collate goes around again to collate the SECOND word in the witness against the first word of the base, and reports a SECOND variant at this point. For example: if the base has 'mat' and the witness has 'black cat' Collate could report that 'black' has been added, and that 'cat' is a variant on 'cat'. See further below on additions and omissions.
6. Still no match: Collate guesses that maybe the problem is word division. So it concatenates words in the base and the witness, comparing as it does, to see if it can find a match
7. Still no match: Collate starts searching for phrase variants: addition/omission/replacement. In essence, it looks further along the text, seeking to find sequences that match, with everything up to the match a replacement/addition/omission. This

is probably the least sophisticated part of the current collate. Collate also has a limit of 50 words for its look up: this might be lifted.

8. After Collate has found the match on this first word: it then looks to check if the NEXT match between this witness and the base is an addition in this witness. The reason it needs to do this is explained in the section on additions and omissions below.

After Collate has done this for this word in the base against this witness: it goes on to do the same for the next witness against this same base. As it identified each alignment, it stores the alignment information for each witness. When it has worked its way through all the witnesses for this word, and has stored the alignment for each: it proceeds through the next stages of adjusting the alignment and finally identifying the actual variants.

After completing, as described, the alignment for the first word of the base against all the witnesses: Collate now goes on to align the second word of the base. Notice particularly what happens when Collate discovers that it has already matched past the next word in the witness: when, say, the first six words of the base have been replaced by the first eight words of the witness. In that case, Collate will skip over that witness until it is collating word 7 of the base: it will then restart the collation by collating word 9 of the witness against that word.

Alignment is NOT variant identification

I have spoken so far only of text alignment, not variant identification. The difference is important. Here is an example:

Base the black cat
A The black cat
B THE BLACK CAT
C The black cat
D The, black cat

For the purposes of text alignment: the collation algorithm should ignore case differences, punctuation tokens, and XML encoding around or within the words. Thus: it should identify the first word of each one of the four witnesses as aligned against the first word of the base. But note: it might be desirable to identify each or any one of the four first words as having a variant at this point. This variant identification is to be done at a later point. For now, all we have to do is state that the first word in each of the four witnesses aligns against the first word of the base.

Additions and omissions in Collate

This is a particularly difficult area. I discovered in the course of writing Collate0-2 that different people want all kinds of different things. Some people do not want to see additions and omissions at all, but only replacements of shorter or longer phrases by longer or shorter ones. When it is an addition and the scholar wants this seen as a replacement of a shorter phrase by a longer one, some scholars want to see the addition attached at the beginning, some at the end. Take this text:

Base: a cat
witness: a black cat

Here are the possibilities:

a] a; black added
cat] cat (writing the addition with the PRECEDING word)

OR

a] a
cat] cat; black added (writing the addition with the FOLLOWING word)

OR

a] a black
cat] cat (as phrase, addition with preceding word)

OR

a] a
cat] black cat (as phrase, addition with following)

OR

a] a
...] black
cat] cat (this is actually the system used in Munster!)

Collate0-2 supports all these possibilities, but does it in a rather inelegant way. Essentially, it tries to adjust for these possibilities WHILE it collates. This is complex and inflexible. Instead, I propose that CollateXML separate completely the discovery of alignment, its storage and its expression. Collate0-2 almost does this, but does not do it thoroughly. Broadly, I began with outputting the variants as the program discovered them. Increasingly I found that one needed to adjust the variation in various ways, and so moved towards separation of the stages of alignment discovery, storage and variant identification. A major benefit of this separation is that it permits adjustment of the variation at the storage point: see next. However, Collate0-2 never quite managed a complete movement to this separation. I propose that CollateXML has this separation at its heart.

The storage of alignment information

So far, I have been describing how Collate discovers alignment. Essentially, Collate discovers, for each word in the base text, for a particular witness, exactly what alignment is present in a given witness at that point. The possibilities are:

1. base and witness align at this word, either because there is no variation (base and witness agree on this word) or because base and witness vary at this word (either as: omission of this word, or variation on the word)
2. base and witness align and there is an addition before and/or after this word (note: this includes the possibility of an addition before the word, omission of the word, and addition after the word)
3. the word is the beginning of a phrase alignment, with or without an addition before the phrase alignment (note: this includes the possibility of phrase omission)
4. the word is the ending of a phrase alignment, with or without an addition after the phrase alignment (including, the possibility of phrase omission)
5. the word falls within a phrase alignment (for example: 'the black cat' replaced by 'a white mouse'. When Collate comes to collate 'black' in the base against this witness, it will find that it falls within a phrase alignment and move onto the next word.

It can be seen that alignment is much complicated by the need to deal with 'additions'. Again, Collate0-2 never quite dealt with this as well as it needs to, and again I propose to remedy this in CollateXML. I suggest that they be dealt with as follows:

1. The base text is seen as a series of slots, corresponding to the words AND the space before the first word, between each word, and after the last word
2. The variants in each witness be aligned against these slots. Thus: an addition before the first word is aligned against the slot before the first word; a variant at the first word is aligned against the first word; an addition between the first and second words is aligned against the slot between these words, and so on.

One may illustrate this with the base 'black cat' collated against the witness 'the black and white cat'. Numbering each 'slot' in the base from zero, we have:

numbers	1	2	3	4
base		black		cat
witness	the	black	and white	cat

Thus: the additions 'the' and 'and white' align against slots 1 and 3. In this system, even numbers are used for words; odd numbers for the spaces between the words. (I am indebted to the Institute for New Testament Research, Munster, for this numbering system, and this conception of the base as a series of slots for both words and the spaces between them).

The adjustment of variant information: a relatively simple case

The principal benefit of the separation of the stages of alignment discovery, storage and output is that it permits adjustment of the variant alignments at the storage stage and before the output.

Consider the case of the following (rather fictitious) instance:

Base: The cat sat on the mat
Witness: The black sat on the mat

Left to itself, Collate0-2 will tell us that the variant is:

cat] black

But in fact, what has happened here is more correctly:

The] The
..] black
cat] omitted

That is: first 'black' is added, then somehow 'cat' is omitted.

We may have many witnesses which read 'The black cat' where the base reads 'The cat'. In this case, at the storage stage, we should expect Collate to look over the variants discovered in the other witnesses, find that in many others we have 'black' added, and it should then adjust the stored variant information so that instead of reading:

numbers	1	2	3	4	5	6
base		the		cat		sat
witness1	the		black			sat
witness2	the	black	cat			sat
witness2	the	black	cat			sat

the stored representation reads:

numbers	1	2	3	4	5	6
base		the		cat		sat

witness1 the black sat
witness2 the black cat sat
witness2 the black cat sat

That is: with ‘black’ matching against the space between ‘the’ and ‘cat’ (as it is in other witnesses) rather than against ‘cat’.

Collate0-2 did NOT do this variant adjustment. CollateXML should do it. In the next section, I consider some possibilities.

The adjustment of alignment information: towards multiple progressive alignment

This matter of automated adjustment of variant information at the storage stage – that is, after the collation of a particular word has finished – is one area where the algorithms of Collate0-2 could be dramatically improved.

Consider, first, this case:

base the white and black cat
witness1 the black and white cat

Collate0-2 will record this as a single piece of variant information: that the whole phrase ‘white and black’ in the base has been replaced by the whole phrase ‘black and white’. It has been pointed out to me, quite separately, by two very different groups of scholars, that this is inadequate (the two groups are: the Münster institute, and the department of Molecular Biology in Cambridge):

1. This does not record that the words of the variant text ‘black and white’ are actually the same as those of the base
2. As a result: suppose that a second witness has ‘green or blue’ for this phrase. To the program (and hence, to any system based on it) there is exactly as much difference between the variants ‘black and white’ and ‘green or blue’ and the base text ‘white or black’ as there is between each variant and the base text. But this loses a key piece of information: that the variant ‘black and white’ is actually much closer to the base than is the variant ‘green or blue’.

CollateXML needs to find a way of adjusting the variant store to show that in fact the variant ‘black and white’ represents not one, but four pieces of information:

1. firstly, that there is a phrase variant (the existing Collate0-2 algorithms do this)
2. secondly, that actually each word in the phrase variant does agree with the base: a further three pieces of information (Collate0-2 goes a little way towards this, but not far enough)

Consider, further, this case:

base the white and black cat
witness1 the black and white cat
witness2 the black and green cat

Here, we should show that witness2 both has a phrase variant AND is a witness for the words ‘black’ ‘and’ – and, furthermore, has a variant ‘green’ on the word ‘white’ in both the base and witness1. One wants an output as follows:

white and black] black and white witness1; black and green witness2
white] witness1; green witness2
and] witness1 witness2
black] witness1 witness2

If we can figure out a way to store this information then we are well on our way to collation nirvana: multiple progressive alignment. But before we get to that place: we have to understand parallel segmentation.

Variant information storage and parallel segmentation

Perhaps the single most important development in Collate2 was the support for parallel segmentation. I write about this in the 'Collation rationale' on the Miller's Tale CD-ROM. The example I use there is

This Carpenter hadde wedded newe a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded a newe wyf
This Carpenter hadde newe wedded a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded newly a wyf
This Carpenter hadde E wedded newe a wyf
This Carpenter hadde newli wedded a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded a wyf

In that article I explained that in the early versions of Collate, we used to collate this by what I called 'base text collation': that is we would compare each witness (54 in this case) word by word with this one base, one witness at a time, and output the variation so:

This] 54 witnesses
Carpenter] 54 witnesses
hadde] 54 witnesses
wedded] 53 witnesses; E wedded 1 witness
wedded newe] newe wedded 1 witness, newli wedded 1 witness
newe] 26 witnesses; newly 1 witness; omitted 1 witness
newe a] a newe 23 witnesses
a] 30 witnesses
wyf] 54 witnesses

We see here that for the first three words and the last word there is no variation, and we just state accordingly that all witnesses there agree with the base and with each other. All the variation occurs on the three base text words 'wedded newe a'. This variation is actually recorded against five lemmata: in turn 'wedded', 'wedded newe', 'newe', 'newe a' and 'a'. Observe that the phrases 'wedded newe' and 'newe wedded' both overlap one other, and also overlap the three words 'wedded' 'newe' 'a'.

The 'Collation rationale' article goes on to explain why we became increasingly dissatisfied with this method. One factor was that it highlighted the base text: by referring all variation to this base text, it gave the base text a prominence which we did not think appropriate. We thought of the base text as just a series of slots on which we hung the collation: but this mode of expression seemed to give it an authority beyond this. It is not that we do not believe in 'edited' texts: just that this base text was not conceived, or intended to be, any such edited text. But its prominence made it look as if it could be such an edited text.

A second factor was the argument put to us by the evolutionary biologists: that where variant lemmata overlap, as they do in the cases of the five variants on the three words 'wedded newe a', one cannot compare directly the different witnesses. Here, we have one set of variants on the phrase 'wedded newe' and a second on the phrase 'newe a', as well as variants on each individual word. If manuscript A has a variant on 'wedded newe' and B has one on 'newe a' there is no way one can compare the text of A and B directly, and make any statement at all about the relationship between A and B at those points.

This defect in base text collation had other implications. We wanted to be able to point at any word in any manuscript and say: what readings do the other manuscripts have at this point? But this was exactly what our system could not do. With our system, we could only say: at this word, the base text has such and such. We could not always say: at this word, here are all the readings found at this point in all the other texts. Similarly, we wanted to be able to compare any two (or more) manuscripts word by word, showing exactly how they differ. Once more, this system could not do that: we could only show how they severally differed from the base text, not how they differed from each other. The only cure for this we could see was: eliminate overlapping variation. This meant that we should refer all variants in all witnesses to the same base lemma. This meant that, practically, the unit of variation has to be fixed by the longest variant present at any point. In the case of the Miller's Tale example: with base text collation we have five sets of lemmata in the three word base sequence 'wedded newe a', and so cannot compare the witnesses on any one of the lemmata with those for any other. To eliminate all overlapping variation here we should have one lemma and one lemma only: all three words of the base text here. All variants on this one lemma are then directly in parallel with each other. The whole text, across all the witnesses, is broken into parallel segments, with text of any one witness at any one segment being directly comparable to the text of any other witness at that segment: hence, the name 'parallel segmentation'.

This is the collation given by the base text collation system, with five different lemmata:

wedded] 53 witnesses; E wedded 1 witness
wedded newe] newe wedded 1 witness, newli wedded 1 witness
newe] 26 mss; newly 1 witness; omitted 1 witness
newe a] a newe 23 witnesses
a] 30 witnesses

Now, this is the collation given by parallel segmentation, with just one lemma:

wedded newe a] wedded newe a 25 witnesses
wedded a newe 23 witnesses
newe wedded a 1 witness
E wedded newe a 1 witness
wedded newly a 2 witnesses
newli wedded a 1 witness
wedded a 1 witness

How did Collate0-2 identify parallel segments? Collate0-2 used a system of variant information storage similar to that outlined above: essentially, creating a table which in numeric form exactly what words in each witness correspond with what words in the base. It would update this table after each word collated in the base. Then, it would inspect the table, and ask: is there a variant lemma open at this point? If there were, then it would not output any apparatus, but move on to the next word, and only when it found no variant lemmata open would it output all the variants on the whole segment of text.

Thus, for the base text sequence 'wedded newe a' it would proceed as follows. It would collate the first word, 'wedded', and discover the following:

wedded] 53 witnesses; E wedded 1 witness
wedded newe] newe wedded 1 witness, newli wedded 1 witness
That is, the lemma 'wedded newe' is still open after collation of 'wedded'. So no apparatus is output, and it goes onto the next word:
newe] 26 mss; newly 1 witness; omitted 1 witness
newe a] a newe 23 witnesses

Now, the lemma 'wedded newe' has been closed. But another variant lemma 'newe a' is now open. So we have to carry on to the next word:

a] 30 witnesses

Now, at last: no phrase variant is open. We can close the segment, and output all the variation found on the whole phrase 'wedded newe a'.

The limits of parallel segmentation: toward progressive multiple alignment

Parallel segmentation has served us well. It has allowed us to remove the base text from the apparatus output completely: on our publications now, you do not see the base text at all. We still use a base text when we collate, but its function now is purely to identify the variants present at each point, and we customarily optimize it for that purpose (for example, adding or rearranging words to improve variant identification). The move to parallel segmentation has other benefits. We can now identify at any point in any witness just what witnesses are present at that point; we can compare any two (or more) witnesses; we can create much richer analyses of stemmatic relations. But we are still not happy.

In the 'Collation Rationale' argument I cite the variants on the first four words of line 646 of the Miller's Tale ('He was agast so of Nowelys flood').

1. He was agast so 33 witnesses
2. He was agast 4 witnesses
3. So he was agast 6 witnesses
4. He was so agast 7 witnesses
5. He was agast and feerd 2 witnesses
6. So was he agast 1 witness

Just as a presentation of the variation at this point, this is quite efficient. But as a representation of the exact linkages between the witnesses, it is rather inefficient. These six variants are presented in simple parallel, as if no two of them are any closer than any other. But manifestly, that is not true. The second and fourth readings 'He was agast' and 'He was so agast' are much closer to the first reading 'He was agast so' than they are to either the third and sixth readings. In turn, the third and sixth readings 'So he was agast' and 'So was he agast' are much nearer each other than they are to the other readings.

With parallel segmentation, once it has found the segments, the collation stops and just presents the segments it has found. In this collation system, all variants at any point are equally unlike. We require some system of grouping the variants within each segment. For this example, I proposed that that the six variants here should be grouped into two variant sequences:

1. 46 witnesses: made up of variants 1, 2, 4, 5, all beginning with the words 'He was..'
2. Seven witnesses: made up of variants 3 and 6, both beginning with 'So'

We can break up the first group still further:

1. 40 witnesses, made up of variants 1 and 4, having the same words but with 'so agast' transposed
2. 6 witnesses, made up of variants 2 and 5, both omitting 'so'

Finally, we note that the two groups 1 and 2 (of 46 and 7) are linked together via variant 1 (from group 1) and variant 3 (from group 2): these differ only in their placement of the word 'so'. We can represent this schematically as follows:

From examination of the variant map, we can see that – rather remarkably (or not!) – this representation mirrors the textual history of the tradition. The original reading is likely to have been variant 1 (33 mss). Three variants descended directly from variant 1:

Variant 5 (seven witnesses) by transposition of 'so', from which a further variant (variant 6, one witness) develops, by transposition of 'he was'

Variant 4 (7 witnesses) by transposition of 'agast so'

The ancestor of variants 2 and 5: both omit the 'so', while 5 adds 'and feerd'..

Indeed, this distribution is consistent with other groupings established by our analysis.

So, here is the challenge I set in the 'Collation Rationale' article, here set out in more detail:

1. Identify relationships between the variant groups found by parallel segmentation
2. Work out a way of storing the information about these relationships, so as to enable different kinds of output
3. Work out the best ways of expressing this information, in some kind of hierarchical or layered form.

At present, we do not have any means of formally expressing the relationships between the variant groups found by parallel segmentation. Here is a draft of how it might be done, using the example above:

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He was agast so
    He was so agast
        He was agast
        He was agast and feerd

So he was agast
    So was he agast
  
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We need an adaptation of the system used by the TEI to hold this. Ideas please!

Variant identification

So far, we have aligned the texts, stored the alignment identification, and then adjusted the alignment information (we hope, through some form of multiple progressive alignment). But we have not yet identified any variants. Now, consider again our example from above:

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A The black cat
B THE BLACK CAT
  
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C The black cat
D The, black cat

Following parallel segmentation, we may now ignore the base. We look at the first word, and find they are aligned as follows:

A The
B THE
C The
D The,

Are these, or are these not, variants of each other? I propose that Collate3 have, for each witness, a specifications object. This will state, for each witness, whether differences of case, XML encoding, and punctuation are to be treated as variants or not. Presume that we direct that case differences and XML encoding are not variants but that punctuation is. We would get the following collation taking A as the base

The] A B C; The, D

Taking B as the base: the variant would appear as
THE] A B C; The, D

Or, if we say that punctuation is not significant, but XML encoding is significant, we will get this collation:

The] A B D; The C

Variant identification and the return of the base

I said above we may now discard the base. To a point, Lord Copper (esoteric joke, see Decline and Fall). There is one critical operation for which we still must retain the base.

The question is to do with the use of variant specifications to identify exactly what is a variant. Suppose for our pair A and D we have the variants THE (A) and The, (D). We have the following variant specifications:

A: ignore case and punctuation
D: ignore case but do not ignore punctuation

We now compare A and D: 'THE' and 'The,'. From the point of view of A: there is no variant here, because we are ignoring both case and punctuation. But from the point of view of D: there is a variant, because we there is a difference of punctuation.

Thus: the variation found changes, according to the point of view. It changes too (obviously) according to which witnesses we are comparing. The only way I can see out of this is to use the base as the measure against which variants are identified, but always do the variant identification using the specifications set for the witness. In this case, presume that the base here is 'The', with all witnesses set to ignore case but not punctuation. We will then have:

The] A B C; The, D

Notice that depending on the base text and the collation specifications, we could get very different results. Suppose that we set punctuation to be ignored in A B C but not D. If we use 'The' as the base text, we get this:

The] A B C; The, D

But if we set 'The,' as the base, we get this:

The,] A B C D

I don't see any way around this. One could avoid this (as Collate0-2 did) by insisting that all witnesses have the same collation specifications. But it has been forcefully represented to me that it would be very useful to be able to specify different treatments of case/punctuation/xml for different witnesses. So we will do this.

February 6, 2007

Datastructures for CollateXML

Filed under: CollateXML datastructures — Peter @ 5:46 am

From the account of the collation, we are dealing with something very different from 'string comparison'. Indeed, the base unit of the collation is the word: we collate words, not strings. Words may be concatenated, or divided: but words are the basis of it all. (This was the form used by Collate).

For each witness, we need the following information:

1. Its sigil
2. Its location (in Collate0-2 this was simply a file name; in CollateXML it might be a url, an xquery or xpath expression, etc)
3. Collation specifications for this witness. See below.
4. For each collateable block: two collateable object arrays. See below
5. For each collateable block: an array of correspondences with the base. See below.

The collation specifications for variant identification

These will control the way what is recorded as a variant against the base. Settings include:

a. case. settings will be collate/ignore.

if collate: Collation will treat differences of case as variants.

if ignore: Collation will not treat differences of case as variants.

b. xml. ignore xml. Settings will be: all/none/nominated

If none: all xml encoding surrounding, within or between the words will be ignored

If all: all xml encoding will be collated, including empty elements, surrounding, within, and between the words

If nominated: only specified xml elements will be nominated. The details of the xml elements to be collated will be held in a further structure (see below).

c. xmlcollate: null unless xml=nominated. This structure is a series of elements to be collated, as follows:

i. gi: the gi of the element to be collated (including namespace)

ii. attributes: Values are all/none/nominated. If all: all attributes and their values are to be collated; if none, all attribute values are ignored, and only element names are collated; if nominated, details of attributes to be collated are held in a further structure

iii. collateattributes: null unless attributes=nominated. This structure is a series of attribute names which will be collated for this element (this could be further elaborated, perhaps, to set conditions: report as variant if the attribute is a particular value)

d. punctuation. Settings will be all/none/nominated

if all: collate all punctuation, as identified by the isPunctuation method

if none: collate no punctuation, as identified by the isPunctuation method
if nominated: collate only specific punctuation identified by the isPunctuation method
The specifications object must also have at least one method: isPunctuation. For a particular pair of strings, this should identify whether differences between them are purely punctuation (in which case, they might or might not be variants) or not.

Two other methods might be required:

isCaseDifference: if it is found that Java's native methods for ignoring case difference when comparing strings are not adequate.

adjustXML: for some contexts, we may need to do more than simply ignore/not ignore XML.

Consider:

ex&per;perience

One might here wish to ignore the &per; element and treat this as 'experience'.

The collation specifications for text alignment

The model here proposed, of separating text alignment from variant identification, presumes that optimal text alignment would be achieved by ignoring differences of case, punctuation and xml. Thus, at the alignment stage, we would use the minimal set of collation specifications for comparison of witnesses with the base.

Hierarchical setting of collation specifications

One would expect that for most collations, one would have identical specifications for all witnesses. In programming terms: one would set the specifications for the class of witnesses, which would then inherit a uniform set of specifications. This design permits that the uniform specification would be overruled for specific witnesses.

The collateable object arrays

The key to Collate0-2 was that it did not collate text strings: it collated word objects. For each witness, it held the words of the text in an array of word objects, numbered from 0 to xxx, and all collation took place against these word objects, with information about variants found stored in tables of numbers referring to these arrays. I propose that CollateXML retain, refine and extend this model. Collate0-2 accepted 'plain text' and converted this to word object arrays as it collated. As it did so, it might remove (depending on various settings) punctuation or other characters from the text to be collated. Thus 'april / that' would become:

word 1: April

word 2: that

Notice that the '/' is here removed. At a later point, Collate0-2 converted the text to

```
<w n="1">April</w> / <w n="2">that</w>
```

This is rather unsatisfactory. The relationship between the numbering of the words in the word object array and that in the converted XML depends on rather fragile assumptions about what is and is not a word. I propose instead that CollateXML recommend that for word-by-word collation, input must be in full XML form, with all discreet elements marked as follows:

```
<w n="1">April</w> <w n="2">/</w> <w n="3">that</w>
```

This has several implications. It means that, because of the problem of overlapping hierarchies,

treatment of elements spanning across words has to be as follows:

```
<w n="1"><hi>April</hi></w> <w n="2"><hi>/</hi></w> <w n="3"><hi>th</hi>at</w>  
not  
<hi><w n="1">April</w> <w n="2">/</w> <hi><w n="3">th</hi>at</w>
```

The advantage of the explicit labelling of every collateable object in the original text as a <w> element with an 'n' attribute is that it makes linking of the collation with the original text absolutely explicit. The 'n' attribute on each <w element can be used to denote each word in the collateable object array, and then used to link to the corresponding <w element in the original. (One might – might – use XPath to achieve the same result: that is a matter for discussion.)

I said we need TWO collateable object arrays for each witness. The first array, as specified above, is to hold the original text: call this textOriginal. But in fact, this is not the text which will be actually collated. The second array is the text which will be actually collated: call this textCollateable.

TextCollateable will have identical structure and initially identical content to textOriginal.

The reason for the two arrays is to make regularization possible. Regularization was one of the great strengths of Collate0-2, and the approach here suggested is based closely on how Collate0-2 worked. As the scholar collates, he or she will see cases where it is necessary to filter out spelling or other non-significant variation. This may involve alteration of word division. Thus, we might be collating:

```
base: the man Cat  
wit1: theman cat
```

It appears that in wit1 one will want to change the word division for 'theman' and regularize 'cat' to 'Cat'. Thus, textOriginal would hold for wit1:

```
word1 theman  
word2 cat
```

while textCollateable must be altered to:

```
word1 the  
word2 man  
word3 Cat
```

Notice that this will mean keeping an offset pointer at each word, indicating for each array what is the corresponding word in the other array.

Putting this together, we require the following information for each word object in each collateable object array:

1. the word itself (including, XML encoding)
2. the n number for the word, to relate to the n number on the corresponding <w> element in the original
3. the offset to the corresponding word in the other array. Thus: for word 1 in textCollatable the offset would be 0; for word 2 and word 3 it would be -1. For word 1 in textOriginal the offset would be 0; for word 2 it would be +1.

June 21, 2007

Goodbye CollateXML, hello CollateX

Filed under: Introduction – Peter @ 1:32 pm

At last, we are moving. Today I began setting up the source forge site that will take all the code as we start work on the program. And in the process, I did what I have been planning to do for some time: change the name of the program from CollateXML to CollateX. Those who have read all the postings on this (of course, all of you) will know the reason for this change. We plan that the program should be able to collate texts in any format whatever, by devising a single canonical input form and then having translators into this canonical form. Thus it will be able to collate XML, sure: but it will also be able to collate many other formats, including indeed old-style Collate 1-3 files.

June 28, 2007

Collate examples, and first task

Filed under: Collate – Peter @ 10:02 pm

We have decided that the logical place to start is by definition of data structures for the common input phase. So Andrew will get on today with working these out. Here are a few example sets for him to chew on:

Base the black cat

- A The black cat
- B THE BLACK CAT
- C The black cat
- D The, black cat

2:

Base the white and black cat

- A The black cat
- B the black and white cat
- C the black and green cat

3:

This Carpenter hadde wedded newe a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded a newe wyf
This Carpenter hadde newe wedded a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded newly a wyf
This Carpenter hadde E wedded newe a wyf
This Carpenter hadde newli wedded a wyf
This Carpenter hadde wedded a wyf

4.

1. He was agast so 33 witnesses
2. He was agast 4 witnesses
3. So he was agast 6 witnesses
4. He was so agast 7 witnesses
5. He was agast and feerd 2 witnesses
6. So was he agast 1 witness

5. Time for some XML:

```
<l id="MI-35-El" n="35">&paraph; <w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">Carpente&rtail;</w> <w n="3">hadde</w> <w n="4">wedded</w> <w n="5">newe</w> <w n="6">a</w> <w n="7">wyf</w> </l>
```

```
<l id="MI-35-li" n="35"><w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">Carpenter</w> <w n="3">hadde</w> <w n="4">wedded</w> <w n="5">a</w> <w n="6">newe</w> <w n="7">wi&ftail;</w> </l>
```

```
<l id="MI-35-Cn" n="35"><w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">Carpenter</w> <w n="3">had</w> <w n="4">newe</w> <w n="5">wedde&dtail;</w> <w n="6">awif</w> </l>
```

```
<l id="MI-35-Cp" n="35"><w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">Carpunter</w> <w n="3">hadde</w> <w
```

n="4">wedded</w> <w n="5">a</w> <w n="6">newe</w> <w n="7">wy&ftail;</w> </l>
<l id="MI-35-Hg" n="35">¶ph; <w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">Carpenter</w> &virgule; <w
n="3">hadde</w> <w n="4">wedded</w> <w n="5">newe</w> <w n="6">a</w> <w n="7">wyf</w>
</l>
<l id="MI-35-Gg" n="35"><w n="1">This</w> <w n="2">carpenter</w> <w n="3">hadde</w> <w
n="4">weddid</w> <w n="5">newe</w> <w n="6">a</w> <w n="7">wyf</w> </l>
6 Some more XML, this time with more encoding
<l id="MI-1-Bo1" n="1"><w n="1"><hi rend="unex" ht="3">w</hi><hi rend="ul">Hilom</hi></w> <w
n="2">ther</w> <w n="3">was</w> <w n="4">duelling</w> <w n="5">in</w> <w n="6">Oxenford</w>
<note
<l id="MI-1-Cx1" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="2" rend="other">W</hi>Hilom</w> <w n="2">therwas</w>
<w n="3">dwellyn>ail;</w> <w n="4">in</w> <w n="5">Oxenforde</w> </l>
<l id="MI-1-Bw" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="5" rend="orncp">W</hi>ylom</w> <w n="2">per</w> <w
n="3">was</w> <w n="4">dwellyng</w> <w n="5">in</w> <w n="6">Oxenford</w> </l>
<l id="MI-1-Ch" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="2" rend="orncp">W</hi>hilom</w> <w n="2">ther</w> <w
n="3">was</w> <w n="4">dwellyng</w> <w n="5">at</w> <w n="6">Oxenforde</w> </l>
<l id="MI-1-Dd" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="5" rend="orncp">W</hi>hilom</w> <w n="2">there</w> <w
n="3">was</w> <w n="4">dwellyng</w> &virgule; <w n="5">in</w> <w n="6">Oxenfor&dtail;</w> </l>
<l id="MI-80-Bo2" n="80"><w n="1">As</w> <w n="2">brode</w> <w n="3">as</w> <w n="4">is</w> <w
n="5">pe</w> <w n="6">boos</w> <w n="7">of</w> <w n="8">a</w> <w n="9">bokelyr</w> </l>
<l id="MI-1-Ad3" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="4" rend="orncp">W</hi>hilom</w> <w n="2">ther</w> <w
n="3">was</w> <w n="4">dwellyng</w> <w n="5">in</w> <w n="6">Oxenford</w> </l>
<l id="MI-1-Cp" n="1"><w n="1"><hi ht="6" rend="orncp">W</hi>hilom</w> <w n="2">per</w> <w
n="3">was</w> <w n="4">dwellyn>ail;</w> <w n="5">at</w> <w n="6">Oxenfoor&dtail;</w> </l>

enough, now!

Email announcing these posts

Sent 6 February 2007 to Joris, Fotis, and other participants in the January 2007 The Hague meeting:

Dear everyone

at the meeting a week last Friday, we had a good deal of discussion about the future of Collate. Since the meeting, very much under the influence of Barbara, I have undergone a massive conversion.

Barbara pointed out that at the meeting, I seemed to be resisting the idea of handing over Collate for others to develop. Indeed I was, and as Barbara pointed out: I was doing exactly what I forever denounce other people for doing: saying 'this is mine! hands off!'

So now, I have seen the light. And indeed, the more I think of it: this is an ideal project for us all to collaborate on. And I was really impressed with the enthusiasm in The Hague for doing this together. So here is my suggestion: we develop the next Collate (which I suggest should be called CollateXML) together. To start off the process, I have created a blog

<http://www.sd-editions.com/blog>

Here you will find a whole series of materials now about Collate, thus:

An introduction

A history of the three earlier versions of Collate

A design outline for CollateXML

How CollateXML should work

Some Datastructures needed for Collate

There will be more to come, but this will get us running! I will put up the code for Collate2, some of it, though I doubt this will be as useful as the explanations given on the blog site.

I'd be glad to hand this all over to you folks. I'm sure happy to help out, and provide test and sample files, etc etc, and offer lots more advice where I felt it might help. I'd say we could set this up as a source forge project and, well, get on with it. One place to start would be with implementing the fundamental word by word collation algorithm set out in the 'How CollateXML should work' should work.

Well, I've thrown out the stone into the pond now. So folks, who is ready to give up a few years of their life getting this to run???

all the best

Peter